

DEGRADATION PROCESS OF CONCRETE STRUCTURES REINFORCED WITH FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER REBARS IN ALKALINE ENVIRONMENTS: LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) material has several applications including military, automotive, and, in recent decades, in civil construction as rebar in concrete structures. They are composites formed by the union of long fibers and a polymeric matrix, which may degrade in alkaline environments, such as concrete. The degradation process occurs due to the diffusion of hydroxyl ions through the polymeric matrix, which damages the matrix and causes the dissolution of the glass fibers. This work aims to perform a review of the literature, describing the methods for evaluating the degradation of FRP rebars and the results obtained by different authors.

KEYWORDS

FRP reinforced concrete structures, Aging and durability, FRP materials and products.

INTRODUCTION

Corrosion process is an important problem for concrete members. Billions of dollars are spent as maintenance costs in countries such as Canada and United States (Abdelkarim et al., 2019; Moura et al., 2021). Damage in FRP rebars may be caused by different factors, such as UV rays, high temperature and alkaline environments (such as the concrete environment) (ACI 440.1R, 2015; Gravina et al., 2020).

The main degradation mechanisms of FRP rebars are the delamination and detachment at the fiber-resin interface. The diffusion process of hydroxyl ions (OH^-) by the polymeric matrix induces the degradation of the FRP rebar. This process results in changes in physical, chemical, thermal, and mechanical properties due to hydrolysis on the ester group of the matrix and the fiber dissolution (Moura et al., 2021; Rifai et al., 2020).

The changes on the FRP rebars mechanical properties results in changes in the behavior of reinforced-concrete structures. Authors such as Dong et al. (2020) and Wu et al. (2021) studied the effect of alkaline solution on FRP rebars and reinforced-concrete structures with FRP rebars, observing reduction on maximum bending moment and change in the cracking distribution (more sparse cracks), indicating that the bond strength was affected by the conditioning.

Experimental methods to evaluate the degradation of FRP rebars and reinforced-concrete structures often consist of conditioning samples in a representative environment, under high temperature, and, optionally, under sustained load (Benmokrane et al., 2020). The sample conditioning may be done by direct or indirect immersion in a representative environment. Some authors, such as Wu et al. (2022), quotes that direct immersion experiments are more severe than indirect immersions.

Reinforced-concrete structures must resist for many environmental and loads conditions. Concrete elements, such as beams, slabs, and columns, shall be designed providing safety and stability during their whole lifespan (ABNT NBR 6118, 2014). This study, therefore, aims to report a literature review

on the degradation of FRP rebars in alkaline environments, addressing the degradation mechanisms, experimental methods to evaluate the degradation, and an analytical analysis to define the representativeness of the chosen method. Therefore, the study aims to promote a better understanding of the alkaline degradation of FRP rebars.

IMPORTANT NOTES

FRP rebars

FRP rebars are formed by joining resin and high-tensile strength fibers. The resin surrounds fibers and protects them against physical impacts and environmental damage. FRP rebars' mechanical properties are mainly controlled by fiber, in which, the resin joins then and distributes the external loads through the fibers (ACI 440.1R, 2015; Benmokrane et al., 2015).

FRP composites may be produced by different processes: filament winding, centrifugal casting, and pultrusion; pultrusion is more common to elements with uniform transversal sections, such as tubes, rods, and channels (EL-Fiky et al., 2022). FRP rebars are manufactured by the pultrusion process, in which continuous strands of fiber are soaked in a polymeric matrix, and resin-impregnated fibers are pulled through a heated mold (Cardoso et al., 2021).

Several fiber-resin compositions can be used to manufacture FRP rebars: fibers such as carbon, glass, basalt, and aramid, and resins such as epoxy, vinyl ester, and polyester. Fiber-reinforced polymers are named after their fiber type: CFRP (reinforced with carbon fiber), BFRP (reinforced with basalt fiber), AFRP (reinforced with aramid fiber), and GFRP (reinforced with glass fiber) (Elgabbas et al., 2015; Rifai et al., 2020).

FRP rebars present elastic and linear performance in tensile stress-strain behavior, characterizing a fragile rupture (Jabbar & Farid, 2018). Under tensile loads, the fiber-resin interface has a relative slip that results in non-uniform stress in the sectional transversal area (known as shear lag effect, Figure 1). The shear lag effect occurs due to the lower slip strength, i.e., the lower adherence to the fiber-resin interface under axial tensile forces. Many FRP properties can interfere with the shear lag effect: rate of resin and fiber, and mechanical properties of the resin and fiber (Başaran et al., 2022).

Figure 1: Shear Lag effect
Source: You et al. (2017), adapted.

Other properties, such as shear strength and transition temperature, are also dependent on the fiber-resin interface. The shear forces are applied perpendicularly to the fiber direction and are mainly resisted by the resin, therefore a low resistance in this direction is obtained (Benmokrane et al., 2017). At a working temperature close to the transition temperature, the rebar shows a reduction in the mechanical properties, due to changes in the resin behavior and a reduction in their capacity to distribute loads through the fibers (Alsayed et al., 2012).

The behaviour of the fiber-resin interface is essential to guarantee the mechanical properties and durability characteristics of the composite material. Table 1 displays mechanical properties of GFRP rebars which highlight the importance of the fiber-resin interface behaviour. It can be noted that the epoxy resin promotes better mechanical properties than the other resins in combination with the glass fiber. And that vinyl ester is, in turn, better than polyester resin. The resin acts as a matrix that not only join the fibers and distribute the loads, but also protects them against abrasion and/or mechanical

damage, and severe environmental conditions, such as water, salts, and alkalis (Benmokrane et al., 2017).

Table 1: Properties of GFRP rebars for different fiber-resin compositions
Source: Benmokrane et al. (2017), adapted.

GFRP rebars	τ_u (MPa)	f_u (MPa)	E (GPa)	ε_u (%)	S_u (MPa)
Glass + Polyester	250 ± 33	1150 ± 59	56.9 ± 2.4	2.02 ± 0.16	47.2 ± 0.4
Glass + Vinyl Ester	258 ± 32	1432 ± 75	66.3 ± 2.2	2.16 ± 0.089	64.8 ± 4.5
Glass + Epoxy	270 ± 45	1573 ± 135	61.8 ± 1.5	2.54 ± 0.015	77.4 ± 2.7
τ_u = Shear strength					
f_u = Tensile strength					
E = Young's Modulus					
ε_u = Strain					
S_u = Interlaminar shear strength (fiber-matrix)					

The fiber-resin interface is vulnerable to deterioration, usually, related to osmotic cracking of the matrix, interfacial detachment, and delamination due to diffusion into the matrix. The degradation of the interface reduces the ability to transfer loads between the fibers and, consequently, decreases the mechanical properties of the composite material (Benmokrane et al., 2017). The main deterioration mechanism of FRP rebars are delamination and detachment on the fiber-resin interface due to diffusion of hydroxyl ions (OH^-) (Moura et al., 2021; Rifai et al., 2020).

Alkalinity and humidity cause the fiber-matrix dissociation due to the diffusion of alkali ions through the composite (Robert & Benmokrane, 2010; Stanciu et al., 2021). Alkaline environments induce rebar plasticization, reduction of the glass transition temperature, reduction of mechanical strengths, and reduction of stiffness (Moura et al., 2021).

FRP rebars reinforcing concrete structures

Reinforced-concrete structures with FRP rebars experience humidity, alkaline environments, and saline environments, for instance (Manalo et al., 2020). A concrete structure in service condition acts under different loading and environmental conditions. The external forces acting on a structure can produce internal micro-cracks, allowing the inflow, for instance, of water on the structural element resulting on degradation of the FRP (Wu et al., 2021).

The inflow of water into the concrete porous medium has the potential to transport different ions, such as corrosive ions or alkaline ions (Wang et al., 2022). The chemical reaction between cement and water results in a hydrated cement paste composed of many hydration products such as calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H) and portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$). The concrete pore water composition varies for each application of the concrete structures. The concrete pore water pH is higher alkaline (12.5 to 13.5), but due to lexiviation and dissolution the pH value can decrease and vary from 12.5 to 10.0 in the most degraded phase when the concrete pore water is defined mainly by C-S-H (Rodrigues et al., 2021).

Dong et al. (2020) used concrete-beams made with ocean water and ocean sand. The beams are reinforced longitudinally with CFRP rebars, and transversely with BFRP rebars. The conditioning was divided in wet and dry cycle process and by immersion in marine solution, rich of NaCl, at 60°C for 3, 6 and 9 months. It was observed a reduction in the maximum force resisted by the beams. Without conditioning, the resisting force was equal to 64.4 kN, but, due to the conditioning process, it reduced to 58.8 kN, 54.3 kN and 44.9 kN for 3, 6 and 9 months, respectively, in the immersive environment.

Furthermore, Dong et al. (2020) notes a reduction in the maximum displacement. Mid-span displacements equal to 40.1 mm were observed for the reference sample and 34.9 mm, 31.4 mm, and 30.1 mm for conditioning periods of 3, 6 and 9 months, respectively, for the immersion conditioning.

For wet and dry cycle process, 48.4 mm, 38.7 mm, and 38.0 mm of displacement were observed for 3, 6, and 9 months of conditioning, respectively.

Wu et al. (2021) observed other variable, emphasizing the influence of concrete cracking on the degradation process of the rebars. The presence of cracks in beams or any other reinforced-concrete element promotes more channels where the external solution can penetrate the concrete matrix reaching the rebars. They studied specimens of concrete-beams reinforced with GFRP rebars immersed in an alkaline solution - formed by calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) and water, and pH equal to 13.5 - without the effect of temperature for eight years, varying the presence of pre-cracking.

The authors observed that pre-cracking has a significant influence in the degradation process, specimens with pre-cracking (APS) resulted in lower load capacity compared to specimens without pre-cracking (AS). The pre-cracked specimens presented load capacity 15.87%, 17.58% and 18.71% lower than non-pre-cracked specimens for 30, 270 and 2880 days, respectively. Table 2 shows the results obtained by the authors in relation to the beam properties, such as: maximum force, fracture energy and displacement.

Table 2: Reduction of mechanical properties of beams
Source: Wu et al. (2021), adapted.

Conditioning time (days)	30		270		2880	
Sample	AS	APS	AS	APS	AS	APS
Force (kN)	12.60	10.60	9.10	7.50	7.60	6.19
Fracture Energy (N/m)	928.60	650.40	411.50	379.10	343.50	252.90
Displacement (mm)	1.33	1.14	0.96	0.96	0.92	0.88

The effect of degradation of FRP rebars on the mechanical behavior of reinforced concrete structures is considered by standards/recommendations through an environmental reduction coefficient applied to the tensile strength of the rebars. ACI 440.1R (2015) and the Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021) propose the coefficients displayed in Table 3. The maximum reduction factor proposed by the cited recommendations is 30% of the tensile strength. The inclusion of the BFRP bars is carried out in the Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021).

Table 3: Reduction factor for environmental conditions
Source: ACI 440.1R (2015) and Recommended Practice IBRACON/ABECE (2021), adapted.

Exposition	Fiber	Factor (C_E)
Concrete not exposed to soil or water	Carbon	1.0
	Glass/Basalt	0.8
	Aramid	0.9
Concrete exposed to soil or water	Carbon	0.9
	Glass/Basalt	0.7
	Aramid	0.8

LITERATURE REVIEW OF THE ALKALI DEGRADATION

Degradation of FRP rebars

Many authors studied the degradation of FRP rebars in alkaline environments, such as Arczewska et al. (2021), Benmokrane et al. (2020), Wu et al. (2022), and Moura et al. (2021). They used the composition indicated in ASTM D7705/D7705M (2012) to prepare the simulated concrete pore solution. All cited authors, except Wu et al. (2022), immersed samples of rebars in this representative solution. Wu et al. (2022) immersed samples of rebars surrounded by concrete.

Arczewska et al. (2021) study FRP rebars in alkaline environment under 50°C, 60°C and 70°C for 1, 3 and 5 months. They observed that the speed of degradation is a function of the solution temperature and the alkaline environment. The authors verified substantial strength degradation under these conditions, with a similar retention on tensile and shear properties, and a faster degradation in flexure strength properties. Furthermore, it is quoted a relation between degradation and rebar's diameter, in which a smaller rebar diameter results in larger speed of degradation, due to the larger ratio of 'damaged' to 'undamaged' areas.

Benmokrane et al. (2020) evaluated the mechanical properties of FRP rebars, such as tensile strength, transverse-shear strength, and interlaminar-shear strength. They conditioned samples in alkaline environment under 60°C for 3 months. The types of fiber and resin governed the reduction of those mechanical properties. The rebars reinforced with glass fibers are higher degraded compared to carbon and basalt fibers. Furthermore, the authors emphasize that compatibility between fiber and resin is important to minimize the degradation in alkaline conditions, observing that glass fiber provides higher compatibility with vinyl ester resin than with basalt fibers.

Different from the previous authors presented, Wu et al. (2022) evaluated the degradation of FRP rebars by an immersion process of samples of rebars surrounded by concrete, and without the temperature effect. They emphasize the effect of pre-cracks in concrete-structures, which can accelerate the degradation of FRP rebars when surrounded by concrete. Furthermore, they stated that, differently from the tensile strength, the Young's Modulus is not significantly affected by the exposure time, environmental conditioning, and sustained loads.

Table 4 displays the results of Moura et al. (2021) that can exemplify the results obtained by the authors cited above. It can be observed a more important reduction on properties of the rebars manufactured with polyester resin compared to vinyl ester. Also, the lower reduction of the Young's Modulus compared to tensile strength and glass transition temperature. Moura et al. (2021) pointed that rebars made with polyester resin displays greater water absorption than rebars with vinyl ester matrix, which leads to the formation of microcracks, facilitating the entry of solution into the polymeric matrix, and to a greater damage to the material.

Table 4: Reduction of mechanical and physical properties
Source: Moura et al. (2021), adapted.

GFRP rebar	Temperature (°C)	Reduction on tensile strength (%)	Reduction on Youngs Modulus (%)	Reduction on glass transition temperature (%)
Glass/Polyester	60	6.4	1.2	11.0
Glass/Vinyl Ester	60	5.5	2.3	8.0

Table 5, adapted from Benmokrane et al. (2017), also exhibits the high retention in the Young's Modulus while an important loss in tensile and transverse strength is observed. The evolution of the rebar degradation with the time of conditioning of the samples is clear. The mechanical properties decrease with the time of conditioning. However, the reduction in the tensile strength for all GFRP rebars compositions, to 5000 hours, is inferior to the 30% indicated by the standards/recommendations.

Table 5: Reduction of mechanical and physical properties
Source: Benmokrane et al. (2017), adapted

GFRP rebars	Time (h)	Retention (%)			
		τ_u	f_u	E	S_u
Glass + Polyester	1000	94.4	99.0	96.6	93.0
	3000	88.8	81.0	94.9	87.0
	5000	77.5	75.0	89.3	79.0
Glass + Vinyl Ester	1000	96.1	98.0	96.5	97.0
	3000	90.7	89.0	92.2	90.0
	5000	84.1	83.0	88.2	87.0
Glass + Epoxy	1000	98.9	92.0	95.5	96.0
	3000	92.0	83.0	93.0	90.0
	5000	89.0	77.0	87.4	87.0
τ_u = Shear strength					
f_u = Tensile strength					
E = Young's Modulus					
ε_u = Strain					
S_u = Interlaminar shear strength (fiber-matrix)					

As described, the degradation of FRP rebars affects different mechanical properties, and this degradation occurs mainly due to the diffusion of hydroxyls and humidity through the composite. Therefore, it is important to understand this process, the methods to evaluate the degradation, and understand how representative is the experimental method. The following sub-sections focus on introducing the diffusion process, the methods to evaluate FRP degradation, and the effect of temperature in these methods, providing a better understanding of the procedures and how to better evaluate it.

Diffusion process through a polymeric matrix

Exposure to alkaline environments is characterized by the diffusion of hydroxyl ions and water through the polymeric matrix. Such exposure results in weak bond strength at the interface (fiber-matrix) due to the concentration and arising of concrete hydration products, such as calcium hydroxide – similar to concrete (Werle et al., 2011) – between fiber strands (Rolland et al., 2021).

The adverse results of the diffusion process are partially recovered after moisture desorption, but the different properties of resin and fiber (such as the thermal and humid expansion rates) cause micro-scale residual stress, and, consequently, microcracks in the matrix or debonding of the interface (Gao & Zhou, 2019). The microcracks may be caused by swelling, hygroscopic stresses, or by mismatch of thermal expansion coefficients (Quino et al., 2020).

The diffusion process may be described as a Fickian or non-Fickian behavior, in which, rebars even saturated due to water in voids, fiber-resin interface, and free volumes, can continuously gain weight or present loss of weight because of leaching of low-weight molecules, resulting in irreversible changes (Quino et al., 2020). The first Fick's Law represents the initial parcel of the diffusion process. The typical curve of moisture absorption for square root of time is a straight line, but then the curve changes, demonstrating a non-Fickian behavior, as shown in Figure 2 (Moura et al., 2021).

Figure 2: Typical curve of moisture absorption
Source: Moura et al. (2021). adapted.

The changes in the diffusion curve shape occur due to the chemical reaction between the composite and the solution, resulting in damage at the fiber-resin interface, and then the continuation of the diffusion process (Xin et al., 2021). Figure 3 displays diffusion curves for GFRP rebars and perforated GFRP. It can be observed the initial behavior according to the first Fick's Law.

Figure 3: Diffusion curves
Source: Eslami et al. (2015); Moura et al. (2021). adapted.

The diffusion process is divided in three stages: absorption dominated by diffusion (and under low-stress levels), absorption dominated by polymer relaxation (and under cracks propagation), and absorption dominated by compound damage (and under high-stress levels) (Arczewska et al., 2021; Xin et al., 2021). The diffusion dominated by the compound damage stage may be subdivided into damage stages, that is the damage as microscopic cracks providing a quick decrease in the material's stiffness, followed by a low decrease in the material's stiffness but with delamination due to micro-cracks developed in the previous stage, and then the most degraded stage, when the destruction of fiber-resin interface and fiber rupture occur (Stanciu et al., 2021).

The diffusion of hydroxyl ions through the polymeric matrix results on hydrolysis reaction of ester groups, which damages the matrix, resulting in the changes of the physical, chemical, and mechanical properties of the rebars (Rifai et al., 2020). Hydroxyls (OH^-) react with the weakest chemical bond in a vinyl ester and polyester matrix (the ester group) according to Figure 4. The degradation reaction of the resin results in the original elements of the ester group: alcohol and salt of carboxylic acid (Moura et al., 2021).

Figure 4: Chemical reaction between resin and hydroxyls
Source: Moura et al. (2021) - adapted.

Accelerated conditioning

The FRP rebar degradation due to alkaline environments is evaluated through direct or indirect immersion processes. The direct immersion process means an FRP rebar immersed in a representative solution, and the indirect immersion process means an FRP rebar surrounded by a concrete body immersed in a representative solution. Wu et al. (2022) state that the rebar direct immersed are more attacked by the immersive environment, providing higher degradation results.

The direct immersion process provides a higher degradation in the FRP rebar's mechanical properties (Rolland et al., 2021). This process allows a full contact area between the solution and the rebar surface area but in service (real) condition the solution does not cover the same area. The indirect immersion process may better represent this effect, in which, the solution percolated through the concrete remains in the concrete pore covering the smallest contact area (Rifai et al., 2020).

The direct immersion in alkaline solutions usually results in a significant reduction of the tensile strength in a relatively low exposure time, which, in an accelerated condition test, can be considered as a severe environment (Rolland et al., 2021). That phenomenon was analysed by Rifai et al. (2020), who evaluate the behaviour of the basalt fiber reinforced polymer rebar (BFRP). The authors noted that the tensile strengths were similar during the first six months of test, but, after six months, the direct conditioning caused a reduction of 5% to 14% in the resistance compared to indirectly exposed rebar. Figure 5 illustrates the direct and indirect immersion processes.

Figure 5: Direct and indirect immersion.

Methods to evaluate the degradation of FRP rebar cannot be done by realistic times. Therefore, the analysis of the FRP rebar degradation often involves an accelerated conditioning process. This means that test samples are exposed to an immersing environment combined with an elevated temperature (Quino et al., 2020).

The temperature has an acceleration purpose, which means that, under a high-temperature effect, the degradation process accelerates (Rolland et al., 2021). The temperature is one of the most important factors that influence the diffusion process, i.e., it increases the moisture diffusion coefficient of polymeric composites (Gao & Zhou, 2019).

Figure 6 exemplifies the temperature effect. It is displayed the accelerated process at 60°C of the movement of molecules from a region of higher concentration to a region of lower concentration, i.e., the presence of more molecules, at time greater than zero, in the region of lower concentration. The increase in temperature accelerates the diffusion process and, consequently, makes it easier for hydroxyl ion to penetrate the resin, degrading and cracking the fiber protection (Moura et al., 2021).

Figure 6: Temperature effect on diffusion.

Methods related to accelerated conditioning are used to predict long-term behavior in a short time but is necessary to relate the accelerated behavior to the behavior of rebars in service conditions (real applications). Some models are used to relate both behaviors, but models based on the Arrhenius' Law are the most common. The Arrhenius' models describe the relationship between the degradation rate and temperature for the simulated environment (Arczewska et al., 2021).

The Arrhenius' Law can be expressed by the following equation (Eq. 1).

$$k = A \cdot e^{-\frac{E_a}{R \times T}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where:

- k is the degradation rate (time).
- A is a constant related to method conditions.
- E_a is the reaction activation energy.
- R is the universal constant of gases.
- T is the temperature.

The degradation rate parameter (k) is often inversely related to the time (t) for a retention rate of some mechanical property of the FRP rebar. Therefore, rewriting the Arrhenius equation for a linear form, using logarithms terms, the Arrhenius' equation parameters can be defined by linear regression techniques from a curve of mechanical properties retention versus the inverse of temperature. Authors such as Rifai et al. (2020) and Rolland et al. (2021) use this method to predict the degradation.

According to Rifai et al. (2020), the Arrhenius predictive model may be done by the following steps: plot a curve of retention of mechanical property versus time for each temperature tested; pick points of temperature versus retention in mechanical property; plot curves of time (in logarithm form) versus the inverse of temperature (in Kelvin). Thus, the last plotted curve is a linear relationship between time (or the inverse degradation rate) and temperature. This curve may be fit to a linear regression to define Arrhenius' equation parameters.

The following equation (Eq. 2) exhibits the relation between two scenarios: the time t_1 for a degradation in a temperature T_1 and the time t_2 for a degradation in a temperature T_2 . This equation represents Arrhenius' predictive model where it is possible to extend the experimental degradation under high temperatures to the degradation (at the same environment) under lower temperatures. The time shift factors (TSF) are used to provide the degradation for different times and temperatures that had been experienced in the laboratory (Benmokrane et al., 2020).

$$TSF = \frac{t_1}{t_2} = e^{\frac{E_a}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right)} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where:

- TSF is the time shift factor (this factor represents the relation between the time to retention at temperatures T_1 and T_2).

CONCLUSIONS

The design of reinforced-concrete structures consists of taking advantage of the best properties of the concrete material (compression strength) and best properties of the rebars (tension strength). Therefore, any reduction in the mechanical properties of the rebars results in reduction in the mechanical properties of concrete structure.

The degradation of the FRP bars due to alkalinity is caused by the process of diffusion through the bar's polymer matrix. The diffusion in these composites is described, initially, by a Fickian behavior. Then, due to the evolution of the damage, a non Fickian behavior is observed. The diffusion results in swelling of the rebars and microcracks in the material. The diffusion of alkaline ions (OH^-) results at hydrolysis reaction with the resin intensifying the degradation process.

The concrete environment is high alkaline, thus dangerous to the rebars. Furthermore, the external environment influences the concrete structure behavior. As discussed, the presence of pre-cracks allows, more easily, the penetration of the external solution through the concrete, and then degrading the FRP rebar.

Evaluate the alkaline degradation of the FRP bars is usually carried out through tests of accelerated conditioning, by immersion of samples in a representative solution at temperatures around 60°C . The direct immersion of the rebars presents more severe degradation than indirect immersion, however it is important to understand the representativeness of those tests, independently of the chosen test method. The Arrhenius law is usually employed to assess the representativeness of the tests, in which, experiments at high temperatures are extended to lower temperatures.

Therefore, to evaluate the degradation of FRP rebars or reinforced-concrete structures it is important firstly to understand the diffusion process through the polymeric matrix and, for reinforced-concrete, the inflow of the external solution into the concrete environment reaching the rebars, and secondly, to choose an experiment method to evaluate the degradation, and then define the representativeness of the experiment.

The literature addresses the test method of immersion of samples in different solutions at elevated temperature in order to evaluate the long-term degradation of FRP bars. This type of conditioning greatly accelerates its degradation. However, there is a gap in correlating the degradation evaluated in the laboratory with the degradation in service conditions of the structure. For example, direct immersion conditioning leads to more severe results than indirect immersion tests. Therefore, establishing parameters that make the results obtained even more consistent with what is observed in real conditions is a field to be researched.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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